

doi:10.5281/zenodo.16899467

Effect of Current Assets Management on Performance of Listed Health Care Firms in Nigeria

EKPEH Uju Chinelo

**Department of Accountancy,
Faculty of Management Sciences,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of current assets management on performance of listed Health Care Firms in Nigeria. In order to determine the relationship between current assets management (CAM) and performance of firms, CAMs proxy variables were used in the study. It includes; inventories, cash & bank balance and receivables while performance on the other hand was measured using net assets per share (NAPS). The study anchored on the Liquidity Preference Theory adopted an Ex Post Facto approach. Hence, data were collected from the annual reports and accounts of Health Care Firms in Nigeria for the period ended 2020-2024. The study used Ordinary Least Square Regression model in the data analysis. The empirical result of the study indicates a significant and positive relationship between inventories; cash & bank balance; receivables and performance (NAPS) of Health Care Firms in Nigeria. Thus, the study concludes that current assets management enhances and improves the financial performance of Health Care Firms in Nigeria. In lieu of this, the study recommended that corporate organizations should ensure proper management of current assets as it enables firm financial performance.

Keywords: Current Assets Management, Inventories, Cash & Bank Balance, Receivables, Performance

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Current assets management is considered to be the primary goals of working capital management (Jain et al., 2023). Current asset management refers to all the actions and decisions of the management which affects the size and effectiveness of current asset. Current asset management requires special attention in present days when cost of capital is rising and funds are scarce. It has been generally established that the performance/profitability of a firm largely depends upon the manner of its current asset management. If a firm is inefficient in managing current asset, it will not only reduce profitability but may also lead to financial crisis. Both inadequate and excessive current asset is detrimental for a firm. The excessive current asset can result in idle funds which could be used for earning profit while the inadequate current asset will interrupt the operations and will also impairs profitability (Chowdhary & Amin, 2022).

It is within this context that this study explores the relationship between current assets management and firm's financial performance. International financial reporting standards adoption requires that current assets are classified by deposit money banks into five major categories: cash and bank balances, financial assets held for trading, derivative assets, loans and advances to banks and loans and advances to customers. Cash and bank balances constitute the amount of cash available to the bank for daily operations. It comprises of cash in hand and demand deposits. Cash equivalents are short term liquid investments that are readily convertible to known amounts of cash and that are subject to an insignificant risk of changes in value. Cash equivalents comprise deposits held at call with banks and other short-term

highly liquid investments with original maturities of three months or less. For the purposes of the cash flow statement, cash and cash equivalents include cash and non restricted balances with central banks. Cash and balances with central banks include cash and restricted and non-restricted deposits with the central bank. The carrying amount of balances with other banks is a reasonable approximation of fair value which is the amount receivable on demand. The amount and quality of cash and bank balances can improve the income of a bank and thus increase the bank's financial performance. This leads to a hypothesis that:

Current assets management is one of the major challenges facing financial managers globally. This is because a proper management of current assets is very crucial in the growth and survival of business and the ability to handle the trade-off between the two is of great concern to financial managers. Several models have been postulated by theorists to determine the optimum level of current assets that can be maintained by a firm and to make a proper balance between it and firm performance. For instance, Onipe et al. (2022) found a positive relation between the cash and bank balances, financial assets held for trading, loans and advances to customers and return on Asset. Also, Nangih et al. (2020) noted that the receivables of oil and gas firms in Nigeria did not positively influence their share prices. Similarly, Ologbena (2024) investigated the impact of liquidity management on financial performance of Insurance companies in Nigeria and the study showed that liquidity management had an insignificant relationship with firm performance.

As indicated above, most of the findings of prior studies were contradictory though, not in health care firms. To contribute to that ongoing debate, this study examined the influence of current assets management on performance of listed health care on the Nigerian Exchange Group where no known study had been carried out based on the available literature. Specifically, it assessed the relationship between inventories, receivables and cash & bank balance (all proxies of current assets management) and financial performance (using net assets per share as a measure of financial performance). To the best of our knowledge, such does not exist

H₀₁: Inventories has no significant effect on Performance of health care firms in Nigeria

H₀₂: Cash & bank balance does not have significant effect on Performance of health care firms in Nigeria

H₀₃: Receivables has no significant effect on Performance of health care firms in Nigeria

2.0 Review of Related Literature

2.1.1 Current Assets Management

Current asset is part of cyclically repeated business operations at periods not exceeding one year, and comprises assets of various nature. The assets of financial character are cash, securities, accounts receivable and prepaid expenses, and those of tangible nature comprise inventory of materials, goods and finished products. The components of tangible current assets require incurring costs of their purchase and storage, and at the same time they freeze capital. Additionally, the maintenance of inventory involves greater risk than the maintenance of the components of financial nature only, as before being converted into cash, it still needs to go through specific transitory phases (Czekaj & Dresler, 2022).

According to Taani (2022), current asset management is the handling of the current assets of a company. Any assets that a company or business has that is the equivalent of cash or can be liquidated into cash in the period of a year is considered a current asset. Current asset management is the process of administration of current company assets that are the equivalent of cash or can be liquidated into cash in the period of a year. The purpose of current asset management is to keep the flow of a company's income and liability in balance. Current asset management includes management of cash, cash equivalents, accounts receivable and prepaid expenses. It helps to maintain a good current asset position by effective debtors and creditors' management. Current assets management program focuses mainly on accelerating of the payments due to the company through continuous follow ups and thereby reduces the time of debt realization considerably (Omaliko et al., 2017).

For the purpose of this study, current assets management was proxy using inventories, cash & bank balance and inventories

2.1.2 Performance

Financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenues. This term is used as a general measure of a firm's overall financial health over a given period of time, and can be used to compare similar firms across the same industry or to compare industries or sectors in aggregation (Mordi & Omaliko, 2015).

Cheng et al (2022) defined performance as the degree of measure organization put in to achieve their goals and advocated that performance goal should be synonyms. Firm Performance should include efficiency and effectiveness. Efficiency means doing the thing right, quantitatively determined by the ratio of output to input. Effectiveness is “doing the right thing” a relatively vague, non-quantitative concept, mainly concerned with achieving objectives. The function of firm performance measurement is not just informing managers but providing a better way to examine the long-term competitive ability and enterprise value.

For the purpose of this study, performance was measured using net assets per share. This was captured as Net Assets divided by Paid up Capital

Figure 1: The Diagram of Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher’s Concept (2025)

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Liquidity Preference Theory

The Liquidity preference theory was propounded in the year 1930’s by Keynes. In his book, Keynes presents liquidity preference theory there as a liquidity theory of interest, a theory that is supposed to fill the vacuum left by what Keynes regarded as the flawed classical savings theory of interest., and rejected the notion that households and business want to hold a constant that, the income velocity of money depends on many complex variable factors (Nangi et al, 2020). Liquidity preference theory suggests that investors prefer cash or other highly liquid holdings. It further holds that investments that are more liquid are easier to cash in at full value, thereby seeing cash as the most liquid asset of the firm (Mordi & Omaliko, 2016).

The liquidity preference theory is relevant to this study because firms prefer to hold cash and other cash equivalents, as a priority, in order to meet their daily obligations as they occur. This is because, without adequate liquidity, the organization may be illiquid and in extreme cases go bankrupt, if not properly managed.

2.3 Empirical Review

Ologbena (2024) investigated the impact of liquidity management on financial performance of Insurance companies in Nigeria using data from 2014 -2023. The study made use of liquid asset, equity capital, dividend, working capital, investment, under-writing risk and size of the firm as independent variables. Employing Panel regression analysis technique, the study showed that liquidity management had an insignificant relationship with firm performance.

Ofoegbu, Duru and Onodugo (2024) studied liquidity management and profit performance of Pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Nigeria using liquidity, debt, receivables and the sales growth ratios as proxies of liquidity management. Data were collected for the period 2012-2023 and analyzed

with multiple regression analytical tools. The findings showed that liquidity ratios and profitability were significant and positively associated whereas the receivables ratio was negative and insignificant.

Akenga (2024) established the effect of current ratio, cash reserves and debt ratio on financial performance of firms listed at the Nairobi Securities Exchange (NSE). Causal research design was adopted. Purposive sampling technique was used to select 30 firms. The data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. It was found that current ratio and cash reserves had significant effects on ROA while the debt ratio was found to have no significant effect on ROA.

Gill et al (2023) for American firms listed on New York Stock Exchange. They used the data for a sample of 88 American firms for a period of three years from 2020 to 2022. They found statistically significant relationship between current asset management and firm's profitability. Furthermore, it was observed that there was a negative relationship between average days of accounts receivable and firm profitability while positive relationship between cash conversion cycle and profitability. As per their finding, the managers can enhance profitability of their respective firms by properly handling cash conversion cycle and also by keeping the accounts receivable at an optimal level. Moreover, negative relationship between firm's accounts receivable and profitability suggested that less profitable firms pursue a decrease in their accounts receivables to reduce the cash gap in CCC.

Olaoye et al. (2023) studied working capital and firm profitability of quoted companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. It used the panel data methodology from 2012-2022. The study showed that cash collection period and cash payment period had a negative impact on return on assets, though the impact was only significant for cash payment period. It was also discovered that current ratio and inventory period had positive impact on return on assets but that of inventory was insignificant.

Niresh (2022) investigates the relationship between working capital management and financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka. A sample of 30 manufacturing firms listed on the Colombo Stock Exchange was used for this study. Data were collected from annual reports of sampled firms for the period of 2018 to 2021. Performance was measured in terms of return on assets and return on equity while cash conversion cycle, current assets to total assets and current liabilities to total assets were used as measures of working capital management. Correlation and regression analysis were used for the analysis. The findings reveal that, there is no significant relationship between cash conversion cycle and performance measures. The study also concludes that manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka follow conservative working capital management policy.

Taani (2022) examines the impact of working capital management policy and financial leverage on financial performance of Jordanian companies measured in terms of net income, return on equity (ROE) and return on asset (ROA). Pearson's rank correlation test, ANOVA F-test, and multiple regression analysis were used on 45 companies included in the industrial sector in Jordan ranked in terms of gross revenues. Results of the study indicated that firm's working capital management policy, financial leverage, and firm size have significant relation to net income. However working capital management policy has no significant impact on return on equity (ROE) and return on assets (ROA).

Wajahat and Hassan (2020) study 37 listed companies in the OMX Stockholm Stock Exchange show no significant relationship between profitability and working capital management policy when grouped as aggressive, defensive or conservative based on cash conversion cycle. The ratio of current asset to total assets of the observations in this study was another proxy variable for working capital management, but the data failed the tests of normality. Because of this limitation, dummy variables were used instead to capture the effect of working capital management policy on profitability.

Charitou et al. (2020) empirically investigate the effect of working capital management on firm's financial performance in an emerging market. They hypothesized that working capital management leads to improved profitability. Their data set consists of firms listed in the Cyprus Stock Exchange for the period 2003-2012. Using multivariate regression analysis, their results support their hypothesis. Specifically, their results indicate that the cash conversion cycle and all its major components; namely, days in inventory, days sales outstanding and creditors payment period - are associated with the firm's

profitability. The results of this study should be of great importance to managers and major stakeholders, such as investors, creditors and financial analysts.

Nangih (2020) examined the relationship between current assets management and stock performance of quoted oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The used OLS model and the results obtained from the analysis revealed that receivables and inventory significantly influenced share price of the listed firm whereas cash did not. The study therefore concluded that the receivables of oil and gas firms in Nigeria did not positively influence their share prices. Thus, efficiency management of a firm's current assets can positively influence its EPS.

Abubakar and Olowe (2019) looked at the impact of accounts receivables management on financial performance of selected quoted firms in Nigeria. The study population of consists of ten (10) firms quoted on the Nigerian stock exchange from 2012 to 2018 selected based on purposive sampling technique. The study used the multiple regressions method as a tool for analysis. The measures for accounts receivable were accounts receivable ratio, debt ratio and revenue growth whereas financial performance was measured using return on equity (ROE). The result of the analysis reveals that accounts receivable ratio, debt ratio and Revenue growth had a positive significant influence on financial performance.

Lazaridis and Tryfonidis (2016) for 131 firms listed in Athens Stock Exchange during period 2012 to 2015. They reported that there was statistical significant negative relationship between profitability measured through gross operating profit and the Cash Conversion Cycle. Furthermore, managers can create profit by properly handling the individual components of current asset which include accounts receivable, inventory and accounts payable to an optimal level.

Prempeh (2015) evaluated the effect of efficient inventory management on profitability of manufacturing companies in Ghana. A cross sectional data between 2004 and 2014 was gathered from the annual reports of four manufacturing firms quoted on the Ghana Stock Exchange and analyzed with Ordinary Least Squares (OLS). The study revealed that raw materials inventory management had significant and positive impacts on profitability of manufacturing firms in Ghana

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Ex Post Facto design was used in the study. It was established in order to determine the effect of the explanatory variables (INV, CBB & REC) on the dependent variable (NAPS) and also because the existing data used cannot be manipulated or controlled. Data were collected from the Nigerian Stock Exchange Factbook and Annual Reports and Accounts of listed Health Care Firms in Nigeria. The population of the study consists of the entire 10 listed firms under Health Care Sector of NSE. It ranges from Fidson Plc, Morrison Plc, Glaxosmithline Plc, Pharma Deko Plc, Union Diagnostics Plc, Ekocorp Plc, May & Baker Plc, Neimeith Plc, Evans Plc to Nig German Chemical Plc. The study covers the period of 2020-2024. Data were analyzed using ordinary least square regression model with the aid of STATA V. 15 so as to examine the relation between current assets management and financial performance.

3.1 Operationalization and Measurement of Variables

3.1.1 Dependent Variable

The dependent variable in this study is Banks Performance and it was proxy and measured using Net Assets Per Share (NAPS) as used by Omaliko and Mordi (2016). This was captured as Net Assets divided by Paid up Capital

3.1.2 Independent Variable

The independent variable of current assets management was measured using, Inventories, Cash & Bank Balance and Receivables. The measurements for the variables are shown on Table 1 as thus:

Table 1: Measurements for Independent Variables

Variables	Measurements
Inventories	Log of Inventories
Cash & Bank Balance	Log of Cash & Bank Balance
Receivables	Log of Receivables

Source: Empirical Survey (2025)

3.2 Model Specification

In line with the previous researches, the researcher adapted the model of Nangih et al. (2020) in determining the effect of current assets management on firms performance. This is shown below as thus:

$$EPS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 REC + \beta_2 INV + \beta_3 CSH + \mu$$

The modified functional model is shown below as thus:

$$NAPS = F(REC, INV \& CBB)$$

The econometric form of the regression modified for the study is expressed as thus:

MODEL:

$$NAPS_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 REC_t + \beta_2 INV_t + \beta_3 CBB_t + \mu$$

Where:

EPS = Earnings Per Share

REC = Receivables

INV = Inventories

CSH = Cash

NAPS = Net Assets Per Share

CBB = Cash & Bank Balance

μ = Stochastic Term

$\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = Coefficient of Regression Equation

β_0 = Constant coefficient (intercept) of the model

'A Priori' is given as: $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3 > 0$

Decision Rule: accept H_0 if P-value > 1% significant level otherwise reject H_0

4.1 Data Analysis

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	INV	CBB	REC	NAPS
Mean	2.7175	2.138	1.9835	1.5975
Std. Dev.	.6452539	.5245912	.4497267	.7563365
Maximum	3.3	5.6	4.5	3.1
Minimum	1.4	3	1.1	.1
Observations	50	50	50	50

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025).

Table 2 helps to provide some insight into the nature of the selected listed health care firms in Nigeria. It can be observed that on the average, in a 5-year period (2020-2024), the selected firms were characterized by positive Net Assets Per Share (NAPS) value = 1.5975. This is an indication that the entire listed health care firms in Nigeria have a positive NAPS with a standard deviation value of 0.7563365. The average inventory (INV) for the sampled firms was 2.7175 with a standard deviation value of 0.6452539. This means that firms with INV values of 2.7175 have a higher performance. There is also a high variation in maximum and minimum values of INV which stood at 3.3 and 1.4 respectively. This wide variation in INV values among the sampled firms justifies the need for this study as the researcher assumes that firms with higher INV values are higher profit making firms than those firms with low INV values.

Cash & bank balance (CBB) was characterized by a mean value of 2.138 with a standard deviation value of 0.5245912. This means that firms with CBB values of 2.138 have a higher performance. Also, there is also a high variation in maximum and minimum values of CBB which stood at 5.6 and 3 respectively. This wide variation in CBB values among the sampled firms justifies the need for this study as the researcher assumes that firms with higher CBB values are higher profit making firms than those firms with low CBB values.

Also receivables (REC) was characterized by a mean value of 1.9835 with a standard deviation value of 0.4497267. This means that firms with REC values of 1.9835 have a higher performance. Also, there is also a high variation in maximum and minimum values of REC which stood at 4.5 and 1 respectively. This wide variation in REC values among the sampled firms justifies the need for this study as the

researcher assumes that firms with higher REC values are higher profit making firms than those firms with low REC values.

4.0: DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Table 3: Result on Effect of Current Assets Management on Performance of Health Care Firms in Nigeria.

Source	SS	df	MS			
-----+-----				Number of obs =	50	
Model	16.82778774	3	5.60929247	F(3, 46) =	2.02	
Residual	127.9299220	46	2.78108527	Prob > F =	0.0012	
-----+-----				R-squared =	0.7854	
Total	144.7578	49	2.95424081	Adj R-squared =	0.6431	
-----+-----				Root MSE =	1.6677	
-----+-----						
NAPS	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
-----+-----						
INV	1.090005	.4527246	2.41	0.020	2.001292	.1787177
CBB	.6180424	.6218156	3.99	0.032	.6336074	1.869692
REC	.1413565	.6244054	2.23	0.022	1.115506	1.398219
_cons	3.354518	1.300166	2.58	0.013	.7374191	5.971617

Source: Result output from STATA 15 (2025)

4.1 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

H₀₁: Inventories has no significant effect on Performance of health care firms in Nigeria

Inventories based on table 3 above was found to have a positive and significant influence on net assets per share of listed health care firms in Nigeria. With a P-value of 0.020, the test is considered statistically significant. Also with a coefficient of correlation of 1.09%, it indicates that inventory management influences firms performance. This result, therefore suggests that we reject the null hypothesis two (H₀₂) which states that inventories has no significant effect on Performance of health care firms in Nigeria performance. We therefore accepted the alternative hypothesis. This means that in Nigeria, inventory management ensures corporate performance. This result agrees with a priori expectation of Prempeh (2015), Charitou et al. (2020) who found significant and positive association between inventory management and financial performance.

H₀₂: Cash & bank balance does not have significant effect on Performance of health care firms in Nigeria
Cash & bank balance based on table 3 above, was found to have a positive and significant influence on net assets per share of listed health care firms in Nigeria. With a P-value of 0.032, the test is considered statistically significant. Also with a coefficient of correlation of 0.618%, it indicates that cash management influences firms performance. This result, therefore suggests that we reject the null hypothesis two (H₀₂) which states that cash & bank balance does not have significant effect on Performance of health care firms in Nigeria. We therefore accepted the alternative hypothesis. This means that in Nigeria, proper cash management ensures corporate performance. This is in tandem with the study of Nangih et al. (2020), Olaoye et al. (2023) who found positive association between cash & bank balance and firms performance.

H₀₃: Receivables has no significant effect on Performance of health care firms in Nigeria

Receivables based on table 3 above, was found to have a positive and significant influence on net assets per share of listed health care firms in Nigeria. With a P-value of 0.022, the test is considered statistically significant. Based on this result, we reject the null hypothesis two (H₀₂) which states that receivables has no significant effect on Performance of health care firms in Nigeria. We therefore accepted the alternative hypothesis which contends that receivables has significant effect on Performance of health care firms in Nigeria. This is not consistent with the findings of Ofoegbu et al. (2024) who found insignificant relationship between receivables and firms performance.

5.1 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined the effect of current asset management on performance of listed health care firms in Nigeria. From the statistical analysis of the study, the study concludes that current assets management influences corporate performance. Based on this finding, it is recommended that corporate organizations should ensure proper management of current assets as it influences performance.

REFERENCES

- Abubakar, Y., & Oloye, G. (2019). Account receivable management and financial performance of selected quoted firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*, 6(6), 141-145
- Akenga G. (2024). Effect of Liquidity on Financial Performance of Firms Listed at the Nairobi Securities Exchange. *International Journal of Science and Research* 6 (7),279-285
- Charitou, M.S., Elfani, M., & Lois, P. (2020).The effect of working capital management on firm's profitability: Empirical evidence from an emerging market. *Journal of Business and Economics Research*, 8(12), 63.68.
- Cheng, M.C., Wang H.C., Lee, C.C., &Teng P.Y. (2022).The new measure performance indicator as determinants of executive compensation and reward, Taiwan.
- Chowdhary, A., & Amin, M. M. (2022). Working capital management practices in pharmaceutical companies listed in Dhaka stock exchange. *BRAC University Journal*, 4(2), 75-86.
- Czekaj, J., & Dresler, Z. (2022). Zarządzanie finansami przedsiębiorstwa. Podstawy teorii, PWN, Warsaw.
- Gill, A., Biger, N., & Mathur, N. (2023). The relationship between working capital management and profitability: Evidence from the United States. *Business and Economic Journal*, 10.
- Jain, P. K., Singh, S., & Yadav, S. S. (2023). *Financial management practices: An empirical study of Indian corporates*. Springer Science & Business Media
- Lazaridis, I., & Tryfonidis, D. (2016). Relationship between working capital management and profitability of listed companies in the Athens stock exchange. *Journal of Financial Management and Analysis*, 19, 26-35.
- Mordi, K., & Omaliko, E. (2015). Impact of medium and short term financing of small and medium scale enterprises on the transformation agenda in Sub-Sahara Africa. *Contemporary Journal of Empirical Research*, 1(2), 15-32
- Mordi, K., & Omaliko, E. (2016). Effect of working capital management on corporate performance; Evidence from listed beverage firms in Nigeria. *Contemporary Journal of Educational Research*, 6(1), 192-213
- Nangih, E., Obuah, C., & Kumah, L. (2020). Current assets management and stock performance of quoted oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting, Finance and Investment*, 6(5), 27-37
- Niresh, J.A. (2022). Working capital management & financial performance of manufacturing sector in Sri Lanka. *European Journal of Business Management*, 4(15).
- Ofoegbu, G., Duru, A. N & Onodugo, V. (2024). Liquidity management and profit of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing firms listed in Nigerian Stock Exchange. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*. 5(7), 1-
- Olaoye, F. O; Adekanbi, E. O & Oluwadare. (2023). Working capital management and firm's profitability: Evidence from quoted firms on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. *Intelligent Information Management*, 11, 43-60
- Ologbenla, P. (2024). Impact of liquidity management on the performance of Insurance companies in Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance*. 9(1), 40-45.
- Omaliko, E., & Mordi, K. (2016). Effect of information content of financial statements on investment decisions of shareholders of listed firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Business and Vocational Education*, 1(5), 257-271

- Omaliko, E., Uzodimma, A., & Ogbuagu, N. (2017). Effect of cash conversion cycle on working capital of firms listed on consumer goods sector. *Journal of Business and General Studies*, 1(7), 92-99
- Onipe, A., Umar, M., Abiola, A., Joseph, M., & Safiya, O. (2022). Current assets management and financial performance: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of African and Asian Studies*, 13, 45-56
- Prempeh, H. (2015). The impact of efficient inventory management on profitability; Evidence from selected manufacturing firms in Ghana. MPRA, NO 67889
- Taani, K. (2022). Impact of working capital management policy and financial leverage on financial performance: Empirical evidence from Amman stock exchange listed companies. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*, 1(8)
- Wajahat, A., & Hassan, S.H. (2020). *Relationship between profitability and working capital policy of Swedish companies*. Retrieved from Swedish University Essays.